

Determination of the Influence of Organic and Mineral Fertilizers on the Change of the Biochemical Composition of Agricultural Fruits

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Abstract: *In the article, the biochemical composition, sugar content, dry matter, acid content of the fruits of agricultural varieties grown in the conditions of Uzbekistan during the growing season are calculated. In the organoleptic evaluation of the fruits of the plant, the results of the study on the condition of the outer skin, roughness, taste, smell, general value and their mutual differences are given. Also, depending on the taste of the fruits, farm varieties are recommended.*

Keywords: *Yield, sugar content, dry matter, acid content, appearance, summer crop, autumn crop.*

INTRODUCTION

To increase the efficiency of targeted research and development of agricultural production in the countries of the world, it is fruitful in production, has a good biochemical composition, high quality of the fruit, universal, suitable for consumption and processing, low temperature, heat, dry researches are being conducted on the problems of studying and developing agrotechnics of varieties with growth properties in different soil and climate conditions. In the assortment of raspberry varieties grown in Uzbekistan, there are not enough varieties with high yield, resistance to various external environmental factors and fungal diseases, high quality of fruits and universal processing characteristics. Enriching the assortment of agricultural varieties with such varieties, increasing them and developing intensive agrotechnologies for agricultural production is an urgent issue in the agricultural sector of our republic.

It is known that the farm provides the population with high-vitamin berries, as well as providing raw materials for the canning and confectionery industry. The choice of variety is one of the decisive factors in organizing the sugar content and chemical composition of farm fruit on the basis of a highly profitable industry.

In the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 6, 2020 "On approval of the concept of development of the forestry system in the Republic of Uzbekistan" PQ-4850, development of ecotourism on the lands of the forest fund, wood, medicinal and other types of import-substituting, export-oriented products production in 2021-2030 in forestry According to the forecast indicators of the production and preparation of medicinal and food plants, 1160 tons of blackcurrant and horticulture are grown and prepared on a total area of 337 hectares in the Republic, including a total of 42 tons of blackcurrant on an area of 20 hectares in Andijan region. The task of raising horses and livestock is defined. These studies serve to a certain extent in the implementation of the tasks in the regulatory and legal documents related to this activity.

The healing power of hojagat has been known since ancient times. A decoction of its dried flowers has been used for snake and scorpion bites. The harmonious combination of sugar, organic acids, vitamins

C, R, V9 and hematogenous compounds in the composition of raspberry fruit is very useful for various diseases such as ulcer diseases, anemia, vascular permeability disorders. Raspberries are rich in antibiotics that have an antiseptic effect on the upper respiratory tract and prevent colds. The fruit contains sugar from 5-10%, organic acids from 0.5 to 2.5%, vitamins V₁, V₂, V₆, V₉, V₁₂, S, D, E, RR, R, K, food additive. There are substances, dyes (up to 1.5%), phosphorus, iron, salts, pectin (0.5-0.9%) [1,4,8].

The wet fruit of the plant is used to make jam, juice, jam, compote, stew, etc.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Researches are being conducted at the Andijan Research Institute of Horticulture, Viticulture and Winemaking named after Academician Makhmud Mirzayev .

As an object of research, the following belonging to different environmental groups: "Progress (Russia)", "Malboro (USA)", "Vislukha (Russia)", "Barnaulskaya (Russia)", "Vladimir (Russia)", "Gigant (Russia)" raspberry varieties were selected .

The research conducted for the purpose of evaluation of agricultural varieties was carried out on the basis of "Method and program for the study of varieties of fruit, berry fruit and nut plants" (Oryol 1999). Mathematical and statistical processing of the data obtained from the research was carried out using the Microsoft Excel program according to the method recommended by BADospekhov (1985) [6,7]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the results of the study, in order to determine the biologically active substances of the studied cultivars, the presence of sugar content, dry matter and acid content of their fruits was determined. When analyzing the chemical composition of the fruits of Khojagat varieties, it was observed that Normal Khogat was 1.9 grams higher than the Barnaul standard, and Herakle (6.2 grams) was 2.9 grams higher than the standard. The largest fruit weight was 2.5 grams compared to the standard variety in Maravilla (7.4 grams) and Herakle (7.4), while Augustina (7.5 grams) was 2.6 grams higher than the standard variety. Geltii giant variety (8.0 grams) was 3.1 grams higher than the standard variety. variety had sugar content of 12.6%, dry matter content of 13.7%, and acid content of 0.7%, while Vislukha variety contained sugar content of 12.1%, dry matter content of 13.2%, and acid content of 0.8%, sugar content in Malboro variety 11.2%, dry matter 14.1% and acid 0.9%, sugar content in Lyashka variety 13.9%, dry matter substance was 14.9% and acid was 0.8%.

It was observed that in the fruits of the summer harvest of Remontant varieties, Progress was 1.9 grams higher than the standard, and Herakl (6.2 grams) was 2.9 grams higher than the standard. The largest fruit weight was 2.5 grams compared to the standard variety in Maravilla (7.4 grams) and Herakle (7.4), while Augustina (7.5 grams) was 2.6 grams higher than the standard variety. Geltii giant variety (8.0 grams) was 3.1 grams higher than the standard variety. variety had sugar content of 12.3%, dry matter content of 13.2%, and acid content of 0.8%, while Maravilla variety contained sugar content of 13.0%, dry matter content of 13.5%, and acid content of 0.8%, sugar content of 13.2%, dry matter 14.6% and acid 0.8% in the variety of Jeltiy giant, sugar content of 11.4% in Augustina variety, dry matter was 14.0% and acid was 0.8%, sugar content was 12.4%, dry matter was 13.0% and acid was 0.8% in Herakles variety.

It was observed that in autumn harvest fruits of Remontant cultivars, Progress was 1.9 grams higher than the standard, and Heracles (6.2 grams) was 2.9 grams higher than the standard. The largest fruit weight was 2.5 grams compared to the standard variety in Maravilla (7.4 grams) and Herakle (7.4), while Augustina (7.5 grams) was 2.6 grams higher than the standard variety. Geltii giant variety (8.0 grams) was 3.1 grams higher than the standard variety. variety had sugar content of 11.2%, dry matter content of 12.6%, and acid content of 0.7%, while Maravilla variety contained sugar content of 12.0%,

dry matter content of 13.2%, and acid content of 0.8%, sugar content of 12.3%, dry matter 14.5% and acid content of 0.8% in the Jeltii giant variety, sugar content of 11.5% in the Augustina variety, dry matter was 13.7% and acid was 0.8%, in Heracli variety sugar was 11.5%, dry matter was 12.3% and acid was 0.7%

Lyashka (13.9%) was found to have the highest sugar content among the common farm varieties, while Maravilla variety (13.0%) was found to have the highest sugar content among the Remontan varieties. Changes in the chemical composition of fruits were also observed between the summer and autumn harvest of remontan varieties (Table 1).

Table 1. Chemical composition of hawthorn fruits (2020–2022), mg% per 100 g

Varieties	Average		
	sugar content, %	dry matter, %	acid content, %
Summer harvest			
Barnaulskaya (St.)	12.6	13.7	0.7
Vislukha	12.1	13.2	0.8
Malborough	11.2	14.1	0.9
Lyashka	13.9	14.9	0.8
Repair varieties			
Summer harvest			
Progress(st)	12.3	13.2	0.8
Wonderful	13.0	13.5	0.8
A giant gelt	13.2	14.6	0.8
Augustina	11.4	14.0	0.8
Heracles	12.4	13.0	0.8
Autumn harvest			
Progress(st)	11.2	12.6	0.7
Wonderful	12.0	13.2	0.8
A giant gelt	12.3	14.5	0.8
Augustina	11.5	13.7	0.8
Heracles	11.5	12.3	0.7

When evaluating the tasting quality indicators of the fruits of Remontan farm varieties, the following results were determined:

Progress standard variety is rated 4.0 for Appearance, 4.2 for Ripeness, 4.2 for Dryness 3.9 for taste, 4.0 for taste, and an average of 4.1 overall. Among the varieties, the Maravilla variety was highly rated with 5.0 points, the Augustina variety with 5.0 points, and the Heracles with 5.0 points. In terms of taste, the Maravilla variety was highly rated with 4.5 points, the Jelti giant variety with 4.5 points, the Augustina variety with 4.8 points, and the Heracles variety with 4.6 points. Maravilla (4.7 points) and Heracles varieties (4.9 points) were evaluated with high scores in the overall evaluation of all indicators (Table 21).

Table 2. Organoleptic evaluation of fruits of Hojagat varieties (2022 5-point scale)

Varieties	Appearance	Ripeness status	Skin condition	Sir water	The taste	The smell	Fruity taste,	General assessment
progress (st)	4	4.2	3.8	3.9	3.7	4	4	4.1
Wonderful	5	4.6	4.6	4.4	4.5	4.8	5	4.7

A giant gelt	4.4	4.3	4.3	4	4.5	4.3	4.4	4.3
Augustina	5	4.3	4.1	4	4.8	5	4.4	4.5
Heracles	5	4.7	5	4.9	4.6	4.7	5	4.9

Conclusion

1. When the chemical composition of Khogat fruits was studied, the highest sugar content compared to the standard was found in the Lyashka variety, which was 13.9%. The result with the lowest sugar content was recorded in the Malboro variety with an indicator of 11.2%. The highest indicator of dry matter content of the fruit was superior to the control in the Lyashka variety by 14.9% and by the Malboro variety by 14.1%. Among the varieties, the lowest dry matter content was 13.2% in the Vislukha variety. When the acidity of fruits was studied, the highest acidity was found in Malboro variety 0.9%, Lyashka variety 0.8% and Vislukha variety 0.8%.
2. When the chemical composition of the fruit of Remontant cultivars was studied, the highest sugar content compared to the standard was found in Jeltiy giant variety, 13.2%, and Maravilla variety 13.0%. The highest indicator of the content of dry matter in the fruit of Khojagat was dominated by the Jeltii giant variety with 14.6% and Augustina variety with 14.0%. Among the varieties, the lowest indicator of the dry matter content compared to the standard was 13.0% in the Heracles variety. When the acidity of remontant fruits was studied, the same indicator was 0.8% in all varieties.
3. **Fruit weight** according to the most big fruits Wonderful and Heracles varieties belongs to being their weight standard type relatively high to indicators have Especially Jeltiy giant variety his own the most big weight (8 .0 gram) with separate stands
4. **Sugar content: Lyashka variety (13.9 %)** has the highest sugar content among ordinary farm varieties, and Maravilla (13.0%) is the leader among Remontant varieties. Differences in the sugar content of these varieties can be a criterion for consumers to select for flavor characteristics and different purposes.

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